

SWAT4HCLS Tutorial: KG Construction with ONTOP

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1 Conversion of tabular data to RDF

1.1 Learning Objectives

After this section, you will be able to

- convert a table of planetary physical properties to the RDF¹ (Klyne et al. 2014).
- query the generated RDF file with `arq`
- understand the relation between long and wide tabular data and RDF triples.

1.2 Example: The planets table

In this exercise, we operate on a small dataset listing the names and selected geophysical properties of the 8 planets in our solar system²:

id	name	distance_to_sun	rotation_period	orbital_period	density	mass	temperature
Q308	Mercury	69817445934.0	5097600.0	7600522.0	5427.0	330.0	700.0
Q313	Venus	108942109000.0	20997000.0	19414148.0	5243.0	4868.0	747.0
Q2	Earth	152098231559.0	86400.0	31558150.0	5513.0	5972.0	288.0
Q111	Mars	249232432000.0	88642.0	59355072.0	3933.0	642.0	308.0
Q319	Jupiter	816520700000.0	35640.0	374335690.0	1326.0	1898130.0	
Q193	Saturn	1514500000000.0	38520.0	929468434.0	867.0	568360.0	134.0
Q324	Uranus	3006318143000.0	61200.0	2651486400.0	1271.0	86810.0	57.0
Q332	Neptune	4537039826000.0	57600.0	5200692480.0	1638.0	102430.0	72.0

This table is in the *wide* format. A wide table has one record (observation) per row, one (typically the first) column is a unique index of that row, the remaining columns contain property values (data), the

¹Resource Description Framework

²Data were queried from <https://query.wikidata.org/>, <https://science.nasa.gov>, and <https://www.esa.int> between December 2025 and March 2026.

first row gives the property names. This format is often used in summarizing experimental data and in relational database management systems such as SQL³ databases.

1.3 Conversion procedure

Our aim is to produce **RDF** triples (subject predicate object) in *turtle* syntax (Becket et al. 2014) For example, this row

```
| id | name          | ... |
|----+-----+-----|
| Q2 | Earth         | ... |
```

becomes the triple Listing 1.

```
:Q2 :name "Earth"@en .
```

Listing 1: An RDF triple for planet Earth in *turtle* syntax.

In other words, to convert from a wide table to a set of triples, for every field in the table, uniquely identified by row index and a column heading, we write

- the row index as a subject, :Q2,
- the column heading as a predicate, :name,
- the field value as object, e.g. "Earth"@en.

1.4 Tabular formats: Long and wide

A slightly different but closely related approach first converts the wide table to a long table. A long table "rotates" or "pivots" the column headers into a new column and repeats ids and column headers such that the first two columns in the *long* table contain all possible combinations of row index and column header. The third and last column in the *long* table is then the *value* from [row index | column header] of the *wide table*. Listing 2 shows a python code snippet to perform the conversion from *wide* to *long* format and, additionally, renames the *id* column to *subject*:

```
# Read data in its original format (wide).
wide_table = pandas.read_csv('planets.csv', sep=",", header=0)

# Melt/unpivot
long_table = wide_table.melt(
    id_vars="id",
    value_vars=wide_table.columns[1:],
    var_name="predicate",
    value_name="object").sort_values(["id", "predicate"])
).rename(columns={'id': 'subject'})
```

Listing 2: Python snippet to convert a wide table into the long format using `pandas.melt()`.

```
|   | subject | predicate          | object          |
|---+-----+-----+-----|
| 18 | Q2      | day                | 86400.0         |
| 34 | Q2      | density            | 5513.0          |
| 10 | Q2      | distance_to_sun    | 152098231559.0 |
| 42 | Q2      | mass                | 5972.0          |
|  2 | Q2      | name                | Earth           |
| 50 | Q2      | temperature        | 288.0           |
```

³Structured Query Language

```
| 26 | Q2          | year          | 31558150.0    |
```

The long table format has 3 columns for `subject`, `predicate` and `object`, in other words, each row has become a triple (`subject predicate object`).

1.5 Naive conversion

Our "naive" method takes the long table and prints out line by line in *turtle* syntax.

1.5.1 Loading and massaging the data

After running the code in Listing 2, we open a *turtle* file for writing

```
with open('planets.ttl', 'w') as ttl:
```

1.5.2 Prefixes

RDF triples are composed of IRIs⁴ (Dürst et al. 2005). To make sure every subject and every predicate is a proper IRI we prefix these terms with the default `http://example.org/planets#`,

```
ttl.write("@prefix : <http://example.org/planets#> .\n")
```

Additionally, we declare a couple of common prefixes from the W3C⁵,

```
ttl.write("@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .\n")
ttl.write("@prefix rdf:<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .\n")
ttl.write("@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .\n")
ttl.write("@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .\n")
```

1.5.3 Long table rows become triples

For the main part we loop over the long table rows and write out each triple in *turtle* syntax (Listing 3)

```
for record in long_table.to_dict(orient='records'):
    s, p, o = record.values()
    if p=='name': o=f"\{o}\{@en}"
    if str(o) == 'nan': continue

    ttl.write(f":{s} :{p} {o} .\n")
```

Listing 3: Loop over long table records and extraction of triples

1.5.4 Semantics

In Listing 3, every record (`id`) is mapped to a class instance of class `:Planet` but without defining that class. So let's declare `:Planet` as a class (Listing 4)

```
ttl.write(":Planet a owl:Class .\n")
```

Listing 4: Declaration of the class `:Planet`

and make every record a planet (Listing 5)

Header columns have become RDF properties, so let's declare them as such by adding triples of the form (`:name a rdf:Property`) (Listing 6).

⁴Internationalized Resource Identifiers

⁵The World Wide Web Consortium

```
for subject in long_table.subject.unique():
    ttl.write(f":{subject} a :Planet .\n")
```

Listing 5: Instantiation of :Planet instances.

```
for predicate in long_table.predicate.unique():
    ttl.write(f":{predicate} a rdf:Property .\n")
```

Listing 6: Declaration of properties

since we encapsulated this block in a with context, we may now close the file by closing the context, or explicitly closing

```
ttl.close()
```

By now, `planets.ttl` contains

```
@prefix : <http://example.org/planets#> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdf:<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
:Q111 :day 88642.0 .
:Q111 :density 3933.5 .
:Q111 :distance_to_sun 249232432000.0 .
:Q111 :mass 642.0 .
:Q111 :name "Mars" .
...
:Q319 a :Planet .
:Q324 a :Planet .
:Q332 a :Planet .
:day a rdf:Property .
:density a rdf:Property .
:distance_to_sun a rdf:Property .
:mass a rdf:Property .
:name a rdf:Property .
:temperature a rdf:Property .
:year a rdf:Property .
```

Let's see if we can run a query it. Query 7 asks for the planets' distance to the sun relative to the Earth's distance,

```
arq --data=planets.ttl "prefix : <http://example.org/planets#> \
    select ?name ?relative_distance where {\
    ?planet a :Planet ; \
        :name ?name ; \
        :distance_to_sun ?distance .\
    :Q2 :distance_to_sun ?earth_distance . \
    BIND(round(?distance*100/?earth_distance)/100 as ?relative_distance) \
    } \
    order by desc(?relative_distance-1.0) \
"
```

Listing 7: Query for planetary distances to the sun relative to the Earth's distance using `arq[fn:3]` .

name	relative_distance
"Neptune"@en	29.83
"Uranus"@en	19.77
"Saturn"@en	9.96
"Jupiter"@en	5.37
"Mars"@en	1.64
"Earth"@en	1.0
"Venus"@en	0.72
"Mercury"@en	0.46

1.6 RDFLib implementation

A more elegant implementation of our **RDF** writer employs the `rdflib` (The RDFLib Team 2026) library,

1.6.1 Imports

We first import the required packages

```
import pandas
from rdflib import Graph, BNode, Literal
import rdflib.namespace as nslib
from rdflib.namespace import *

from pprint import pprint
```

1.6.2 Namespaces and Prefixes

We are going to construct a `rdflib.Graph` with properly set prefixes (aka namespace bindings in `rdflib` speak). First add some standard namespaces:

```
graph = Graph(bind_namespaces='core')
```

and a custom namespace, identical to the base URL and also set it to be the default namespace/prefix.

```
planets_ns = nslib.Namespace("http://example.org/planets#")
graph.bind("planets", planets_ns)
graph.bind("", planets_ns)
```

1.6.3 Semantics

Now let's define the `:Planets` class

```
graph.add((planets_ns.Planet, RDF.type, OWL['Class']))
```

Our *turtle* so far:

```
@base <http://example.org/planets#> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix planets: <http://example.org/planets#> .

<Planet> a owl:Class .
```

Now let's add the properties by looping over the wide table columns

```
for column in wide_table.columns[1:]:
    graph.add((planets_ns[column], RDF.type, RDF.Property))
```

yielding the graph

```
@prefix : <http://example.org/planets#> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .

:Planet a owl:Class .

:day a rdf:Property .

:density a rdf:Property .

:distance_to_sun a rdf:Property .

:mass a rdf:Property .

:name a rdf:Property .

:temperature a rdf:Property .

:year a rdf:Property .
```

1.6.4 Statements

And finally loop over the rows in our long table and convert each row to a triple, inserted into our graph

```
for record in long_table.to_dict(orient='records'):
    id, prop, val = record.values()
    graph.add((planets_ns[id], RDF.type, planets_ns.Planet))
    if prop == 'name': obj = Literal(val, lang='en')
    else: obj = Literal(val)
    graph.add((planets_ns[id], planets_ns[prop], obj))
```

1.6.5 Serialization to *turtle*

To obtain a string representing the graph in *turtle* syntax, run

```
ttl = graph.serialize()
```

1.6.6 Write results to file

Adding a filename argument to `graph.serialize()`, we can save the graph in a *turtle* file or any other serialization format,

```
graph.serialize('planets.ttl')
```

The resulting file contains the same data as the one obtained from the "naive" conversion (section 1.5) although better cleaned up.

```
@prefix : <http://example.org/planets#> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
```

```

:Q111 a :Planet ;
    :day 8.8642e+04 ;
    :density 3.9335e+03 ;
    :distance_to_sun 2.492324e+11 ;
    :mass 6.42e+02 ;
    :name "Mars"@en ;

```

...

```

:mass a rdf:Property .

```

```

:name a rdf:Property .

```

```

:temperature a rdf:Property .

```

```

:year a rdf:Property .

```

```

:Planet a owl:Class .

```

1.6.7 SPARQL query

Let's run the following query with `arq` utility to test the integrity of our generated **RDF** file. .

```

arq --data=planets.ttl "\
prefix : <http://example.org/planets#> \
select ?name ?relative_year where { \
    ?planet a :Planet; \
        :name ?name ; \
        :year ?planet_year . \
    :Q2 :year ?earth_year . \
    BIND(round(100 * ?planet_year / ?earth_year)/100 as ?relative_year) \
} \
order by ?desc(?relative_year) \
"

```

Listing 8: Query for the length of a year relative to the terrestrial year using `arq`.

```

-----
| name          | relative_year |
=====
| "Mercury"@en | 0.24e0        |
| "Venus"@en   | 0.62e0        |
| "Earth"@en   | 1.0e0         |
| "Mars"@en    | 1.88e0        |
| "Jupiter"@en| 11.86e0       |
| "Saturn"@en  | 29.45e0       |
| "Uranus"@en  | 84.02e0       |
| "Neptune"@en| 164.8e0       |
-----

```

1.7 Assignment: Moons dataset

The file `moons.csv` contains data about the moons in our solar system. Convert it to a turtle formatted **RDF** file. How do you treat the data in `mother_planet_id` column?

Test your result by running Query 9 and check you get the response below.

```

arq --data=moons.ttl "prefix : <http://example.org/planets#> \
  select ?planet (count(?moon) as ?moons) where { \
    ?moon a :Moon ; \
      :name ?name ;\
      :mother_planet_id ?planet . \
  } \
  group by ?planet \
  order by desc(?moons) \
"

```

Listing 9: Querying for the number of moons per planet (as listed in wikidata).

```

-----
| planet | moons |
=====
| :Q193  | 22    |
| :Q324  | 16    |
| :Q319  | 8     |
| :Q2    | 2     |
| :Q332  | 1     |
-----

```

1.7.1 Solution

Listing 10 shows a possible solution to Section 1.7 using python and the `rdflib` package.

2 Mapping of relational databases to RDF

2.1 Learning objectives

After completing this section, you will

- have an overview of the OBDA⁶ mapping language
- be able to configure and launch ontop's built-in SPARQL⁷ endpoint
- have written your own mappings for a SQL database.
- understand the role of ontologies in ontop.

2.2 Introduction

In section 1 we saw how to map a wide table to RDF. Data in RDBs⁸ are not much different. A RDB consists of one or multiple wide tables. Each table has a primary key column, indexing the records in that row. Relations between records are established through foreign key columns. Consider the two tables `planets.csv` and `moons.csv`. In both tables, the `id` column is the primary key, indexing the planets and moons in their table, respectively. The `moons.csv` table has a column `mother_planet_id`, relating that moon to its planet. Entries in the `mother_planet_id` column are the primary keys (`id`) of the `planets.csv` table, hence they are foreign keys in the `moons.csv` table.

⁶Ontology Based Data Access

⁷SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language

⁸Relational Databases

```

# Imports
import pandas
from rdflib import Graph, BNode, Literal
import rdflib.namespace as nslib
import numpy
from rdflib.namespace import *

from pprint import pprint

# RDF Setup
graph = Graph(bind_namespaces='core')

planets_ns = nslib.Namespace("http://example.org/planets#")
graph.bind("planets", planets_ns)
graph.bind("", planets_ns)
graph.add((planets_ns.Moon, RDF.type, OWL['Class']))

# Load csv data and convert to long table
wide_table = pandas.read_csv('moons.csv', sep=",", header=0)

long_table = wide_table.melt(id_vars="id",
                             value_vars=wide_table.columns[1:],
                             var_name="property_name",
                             value_name="property value").sort_values(["id", "property_name"])

# Loop over pandas records
for column in wide_table.columns[1:]:
    graph.add((planets_ns[column], RDF.type, RDF.Property))

for record in long_table.to_dict(orient='records'):
    id, prop, val = record.values()
    graph.add((planets_ns[id], RDF.type, planets_ns.Moon))
    if str(val) == 'nan':
        continue
    if prop == 'mother_planet_id':
        graph.add((planets_ns[id], planets_ns[prop], planets_ns[val]))
    else:
        if prop == 'name': graph.add((planets_ns[id], planets_ns[prop], Literal(val, lang='en')))
        else: graph.add((planets_ns[id], planets_ns[prop], Literal(val)))

# Serialize to turtle
graph.serialize('moons.ttl')

```

Listing 10: Python script to convert `moons.csv` to RDF

2.3 The ontop mapping language

Ontop (Calvanese et al. 2015) provides the **OBDA** mapping language, libraries, and command line interfaces for mapping `glspl{rdb}` to **RDF** using the principles we encountered in Section 1. **OBDA** is compatible with the R2RML⁹ standard (Das et al. 2012). Mapping **RDBs** to **RDF** is often called Virtualization or Virtual Knowledge Graph Construction, Xiao et al. 2019 explains the details.

An **OBDA** mapping is a pair of **source** query and **target** triples. The **source** is a **SQL** **SELECT** query. The **target** statement is a templated **RDF** statement in a syntax similar *turtle* which is expanded over the **source** query response. As an example, let's reconsider listing 1 in Section 2.3.1.

2.3.1 Example: Planets and names

We aim for triples such as

```
:Q2 :name "Earth"@en .
:Q313 :name "Venus"@en .
...
```

to be the graph representation of the `planets` table which is part of the `solar_system` **RDB**.

Source query The **source** query yield the required data for the targeted triple, so we query for the planet's `id`, and its `name`:

```
SELECT id, name FROM planets;
```

Listing 11: SQL **SELECT** statement for planet `name` and `id`.

and receive

id	name
Q308	Mercury
Q313	Venus
Q2	Earth
Q111	Mars
Q319	Jupiter
Q193	Saturn
Q324	Uranus
Q332	Neptune

Target triple template The **target** triple template in this example is

```
:{id} :name "{name}"@en .
```

Curly braces `{..}` are *template* arguments pointing to column names in the **SQL** response table. Upon execution of the mapping, template arguments are replaced by the values in the respective column. For every row in the **SQL** response, values in the column `id` replace the `{id}` template argument in the target triple and values in the `name` column replace the `{name}` template argument. This generates as many triples as there are rows in the **source** query response.

2.4 Target triple structure

Depending on its position in the triple, different terms are supported in **OBDA** targets¹⁰

⁹Relational To RDF Mapping

¹⁰Consult the [ontop mapping language guide](#) for more details.

2.4.1 Subjects

A subject may be one of

1. **IRI or blank node constant:** `<http://example.org/Image>`, `omecore:Image`, `_:MapAnnotation`
2. **IRI or blank node template:** `<http://example.org/Image/{id}>`, `omesite:{cls}`, `_: {map_annotation}`
3. **IRI or blank node column:** taken directly from the source query: `<{iri}>`

2.4.2 Predicates

1. **IRI constant:** `<http://example.org/property>`, `rdfs:label`
2. **IRI template:** `<http://example.org#{map_key}>`
3. **IRI column:** `<{prefixed_key}>`
4. **Instance of property:** `rdf:type`, `a`

2.4.3 Objects

1. **IRI or blank node constant:** `<http://example.org/Dataset>`, `omecore:Dataset`, `_:B1`
2. **IRI or blank node template:** `<http://example.org/Image/{id}>`, `img:{id}`, `_: {map_annotation_value}`
3. **IRI or blank node column:** `<{object_iri}>`
4. **Literal constant:**
 - (a) **Implicitly typed literal:** `123`, `3.14`, `"John Adams"`
 - (b) **Explicitly typed literal:** `"123"^^xsd:integer`, `"3.14"^^xsd:float`, `"John Adams"^^xsd:string`, `"2026-03-23T09:00:00"^^xsd:dateTime`
 - (c) **Language tagged literals:** `"Phase contrast imaging"@en`
5. **Literal template:** `"{first_name} {last_name}"`
6. **Literal column:** `{name}`, can be typed or tagged: `"{name}"^^xsd:string`, `"{name}"@fr`

IRI and blank node templates apply "%-encoding" to special characters or whitespace, IRI columns are assumed to be valid IRIs.

2.5 Combining multiple tables

Often, one has to combine multiple tables into one to generate a "view" which contains all the columns needed for a target template. Suppose for example, we have the target

```
:Moon/{id} :mother_planet_mass {mother_planet_mass} .
```

While `id` certainly comes from the primary key column `id` in the `moons` table, the object value `mother_planet_mass` must be obtained from the `planets` table for each moon's mother planet. A JOIN on `moons` and `planets` generates the needed view,

```
SELECT moons.id AS id,
       planets.mass AS mother_planet_mass
FROM moons JOIN planets
      ON moons.mother_planet_id = planets.id
ORDER BY id
LIMIT 10
```

Listing 12: A SQL JOIN query on `moons` and `planets` returning the mass of each moon's mother planet.

id	mother_planet_mass
Q15034	568360
Q15037	568360
Q15040	568360
Q15047	568360
Q15050	568360
Q15629	86810
Q15633	86810
Q15637	86810
Q15643	86810
Q15644	86810

2.6 Ontologies

In contrast to `arq`, `ontop` supports reasoning over supplied ontologies which can greatly improve `ontop`'s performance and enable inference. Remember that we added class and property declarations to both `planets.ttl` and `moons.ttl` in the warmup exercise Section 1. Within the `ontop` framework, such declarations are collected in the mapping ontology. The ontology enables inference of relations among **RDF** nodes which are not explicitly encoded in the **RDF** file or in the source database. The statement in Listing 13 implicitly makes every subject occurring in a triple involving the `:distance_to_sun` property a `:Planet` class instance.

```
:distance_to_sun a rdf:Property;
                rdfs:domain :Planet .
```

Listing 13: Solar system ontology statement about the `:distance_to_sun` property

Furthermore, 3rd party ontologies and vocabularies can be imported into the mapping ontology, allowing for even richer inference.

2.7 Hands-on session

2.7.1 Install `ontop cli`

See Appendix B.2 for installation instructions for the `ontop` command line interface (`ontop-cli`).

2.7.2 `Ontop config`

`Ontop` needs to be configured with database connection parameters for the underlying **RDB**. The tutorial repository contains a minimal `ontop` setup in the `solar_system_vkg/` directory, consisting of four files

```
solar_system_vkg
|-- solar_system.properties
|-- solar_system.obda
|-- solar_system.ttl
`-- portal.toml
```

1 directory, 4 files

Properties file `:PrTIES: :I 5c206f79-2093-4bb1-991f-dafefa42e3ad :E` The `Properties` file contains the database URL, user and password and refers to the **JDBC**¹¹ for the specific **SQL** flavour (e.g. `postgresql`, `mysql`, ...). The `jdbc` driver jar file must be downloaded separately from `ontop` and saved to the `jdbc` subdirectory of the `ontop` installation.

¹¹Java Database Connector

```
In case, we edit the properties file solar_system.properties as #+: planets.ontop.properties #+N_src
bash :eval no :exports code :tangle solar_system.vkg/solar_system.properties Mments welcome here .pass-
word=solar .user=solar_system .url=jdbc\:postgresql\://localhost\:5432/solar_system .driver=org.postgresql.Driver
#+Src
```

Mapping file :PrTIES: :I 0d2522a7-a8ec-4472-8d9f-0313cdc0bc32 :E ThS:obda file contains the mapping declarations, see Section 2.7.4 for details.

Ontology file As discussed, an ontology is not mandatory but may cause significant performance gains in terms of query response time. The ontology file is a plain *ttl* file, it's overall structure is

```
# solar_system.ttl

<<solar_system.ttl.prefixes>>

<<solar_system.ttl.ontology_declaration>>

<<solar_system.ttl.properties>>

<<solar_system.ttl.classes>>
```

Listing 14: Overall architecture of the solar system mapping ontology file

Here and in the following, `<<...>>` mark placeholders to be completed in other, referenced code listings, following a literate programming (Knuth 1984) approach.

Prefixes We add a number of standard prefixes and our `planets:` prefix to the ontology, as well as a base IRI.

```
@prefix : <http://example.org/planets#> .
@prefix this: <http://example.org/planets#> .
@prefix planets: <http://example.org/planets#> .
@prefix dc: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix xml: <http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix obda: <https://w3id.org/obda/vocabulary#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@base <http://example.org/planets#> .
```

Ontology declaration Second comes the declaration of the ontology itself along with some annotations and a license.

```
# Ontology declaration and annotation
<http://example.org/ontologies/solar_system> rdf:type owl:Ontology ;
dcterms:license "https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/" ;
rdfs:label "Solar System Ontology" ;
skos:definition "Ontology for the Solar System" .
```

Properties The Properties section consists of annotation properties, Data properties, (and Object properties). We first take care of the annotation properties which are already used in the ontology declaration above.

```
# Annotation properties
## License
dcterms:license rdf:type owl:AnnotationProperty .

## Definition
skos:definition rdf:type owl:AnnotationProperty .

## Label
rdfs:label rdf:type owl:AnnotationProperty .
```

Classes Since we're dealing with objects of type *Planet*, it may make sense to define such a class:

```
# Classes
## Planet
planets:Planet rdf:type owl:Class .
```

With this minimal ontology, we should be able to start our ontop endpoint

Portal file The portal `portal.toml` contains example queries to be added to the ontop **SPARQL** endpoint. It needs not to be present.

2.7.3 Launch ontop endpoint

SSH Tunnel (optional) For security reasons, it is not advisable to expose the postgresql via direct TCP/IP connection by opening the port (5432) on the server. Instead, we connect to the server through a `ssh tunnel`, e.g.

```
ssh -l <user> -fN -L5433:localhost:5432 <remote sql server>
```

The command returns without further response, meaning the tunnel was established successfully and you can now connect to the *remote* database by pointing your `sql` client (e.g. `psql`) to localhost on port 5433 (`psql -h localhost -p 5433 ...`).

In this tutorial, the database runs on the presenter's laptop, hostname `localhost`, on port 5432, the default postgres port.

Launch ontop endpoint We can now launch the ontop endpoint with it's minimal config (that is without an ontology). In `solar_system_vkg/`, run

```
../ontop-cli/ontop endpoint --properties solar_system.properties \  
    --mapping solar_system.obda \  
    --portal=portal.toml \  
    --dev
```

Listing 15: Launch ontop endpoint for the planets database.

The `--dev` flag activates development mode in which changes to the mapping or ontology files trigger automatic restart of the endpoint. Sometimes the server has to be killed and restarted manually, so keep an eye on the log. The `portal.toml` file contains example queries.

The above command should produce output similar to

```

##### # # ##### #####
# # ## # # # # # #
# # # # # # # #####
# # # ## # # # #
##### # # # ##### #

```

```

v5.4.0
(Java 17.0.18, Linux 6.8.0-94-generic)

```

```

-INFO in i.u.i.o.e.OntopEndpointApplication - Starting OntopEndpointApplication v5.4.0 using Ja
-INFO in i.u.i.o.e.OntopEndpointApplication - No active profile set, falling back to 1 default
-INFO in o.s.b.w.e.tomcat.TomcatWebServer - Tomcat initialized with port(s): 8080 (http)
-INFO in o.a.coyote.http11.Http11NioProtocol - Initializing ProtocolHandler ["http-nio-8081"]
-INFO in o.a.catalina.core.StandardService - Starting service [Tomcat]
-INFO in o.a.catalina.core.StandardEngine - Starting Servlet engine: [Apache Tomcat/9.0.108]
-INFO in o.a.c.c.C.[Tomcat].[localhost].[/] - Initializing Spring embedded WebApplicationContext
-INFO in o.s.b.w.s.c.ServletWebServerApplicationContext - Root WebApplicationContext: initializ
-INFO in i.u.i.o.a.impl.OntopQueryEngineImpl - Ontop has completed the setup and it is ready fo
-INFO in i.u.i.o.r.r.i.OntopVirtualRepository - Ontop virtual repository initialized successful
-INFO in o.s.b.a.e.web.EndpointLinksResolver - Exposing 1 endpoint(s) beneath base path '/actua
-INFO in o.a.coyote.http11.Http11NioProtocol - Starting ProtocolHandler ["http-nio-8081"]
-INFO in o.s.b.w.e.tomcat.TomcatWebServer - Tomcat started on port(s): 8080 (http) with context
-INFO in i.u.i.o.e.OntopEndpointApplication - Started OntopEndpointApplication in 3.041 seconds

```

Now open <http://localhost:8080> to access the ontop SPARQL UI. For API queries, the endpoint URL is <http://localhost:8080/sparql>.

Try to run a simple query by entering

```
select * where {?sub ?pred ?obj}
```

Listing 16: Minimal SPARQL query on the minimally configured ontop endpoint serving the solar system KG.

Running Query 16, should return

sub	pred	obj
http://example.org/planets#Planet/Q308	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://example.org/planets#Planet
http://example.org/planets#Planet/Q313	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://example.org/planets#Planet
http://example.org/planets#Planet/Q2	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://example.org/planets#Planet
http://example.org/planets#Planet/Q111	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://example.org/planets#Planet
http://example.org/planets#Planet/Q319	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://example.org/planets#Planet
http://example.org/planets#Planet/Q193	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://example.org/planets#Planet
http://example.org/planets#Planet/Q324	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://example.org/planets#Planet
http://example.org/planets#Planet/Q332	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	http://example.org/planets#Planet

2.7.4 Structure of the mapping file

The general structure of the OBDA file is

```
[PrefixDeclaration]
```

```
<<solar_mapping_prefixes>>
```

```
[MappingDeclaration] @collection [[
```

```
<<solar_mappings_collection>>
]]
```

Placeholders in double carets <<...>> mark the locations in the *obda* file to be filled with prefix declarations and mapping definitions, respectively. Be careful to close all single and double brackets []].

The syntax for prefixes is

```
:                http://example.org/planets#
dc:              http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/
owl:            http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#
rdf:            http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
xml:            http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace
xsd:            http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#
obda:           https://w3id.org/obda/vocabulary#
rdfs:           http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
skos:           http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#
this:          http://example.org/planets#
dcterms:        http://purl.org/dc/terms/
planets:        http://example.org/planets#
```

Each mapping consists of a mapping Id, a target definition (multiline ok) and a source definition (multiline ok, no semicolon!). Mappings are separated by blank lines.

```
mappingId <<mapping_id_or_name>>
target    <<target template triple(s)>>
source    <<source sql query>>

mappingId <<mapping_id_or_name>>
target    <<target template triple(s)>>
source    <<source sql query>>

...

```

Listing 17: Structure of *obda* mapping definitions

2.7.5 Test driven development

We'll develop the mappings in a test-driven fashion by iterating over these items:

1. **Requirement:** State a requirement in the form of a query we would like to submit
2. **Test** Formulate the requirement as a test, checking the required query returns the correct result
3. **Implement** the mapping such that the test passes.

2.7.6 Get column names in planets table

The following SQL query returns the column names in the `planets` table:

```
select column_name from information_schema.columns where table_name = 'planets';

| column_name      |
|-----|
| temperature      |
| density           |
| mass              |
| distance_to_sun  |
```

```
| rotation_period |
| orbital_period |
| name           |
| id             |
```

2.7.7 Prefixes

Unless otherwise stated, we assume the following two prefixes are part of all SPARQL queries

```
PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
```

2.7.8 Number of planets

Requirement Our first **requirement** is that we want to be able to query the number of planets in the solar system,

```
PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
```

```
select (count(?planet) as ?nplanets) where {
  ?planet a :Planet .
}
```

and the expected answer is, of course, 8.

Running this query in our ontop endpoint actually produces the correct answer as the original mapping file already contains the declaration

```
mappingId planet-id
target    :Planet/{id} a :Planet .
source    select id from planets
```

But let's still follow the test driven paradigm and write a test which will make sure that 8 **always** comes out, even when we now start making changes to our mappings.

Test Our **test** for the above requirement is a SPARQL ASK query:

```
PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

ask where {
  {
    select (count(?planet) as ?nplanets) where {
      ?planet a :Planet .
    }
  }
  filter(?nplanets="8"^^xsd:integer)
}
```

Confirmation Run the query in the ontop query interface at <http://localhost:8080> and confirm the result.

Actually, this test is also among the example queries in the "Test" tab of our ontop SPARQL endpoint, besides a number of other test queries.

2.7.9 Planet names

Requirement Our next requirement is that we want to be able to query for planet **names**. Query 18 should return the name of each planet.

```
select ?planet ?name where {
  ?planet a :Planet;
         :name ?name .
}
```

Listing 18: SPARQL query for planets and their names.

Running Query 18 in the ontop SPARQL endpoint will fail at this point.

Test We write a test checking that planet Q2's name is "Earth" in the English language

```
ask where {
  {
    values ?planet { :Q2 }
  }
  filter(?name="Earth"@en)
}
```

Listing 19: SPARQL ASK query asserting planet :Q2's name in English is "Earth".

Implementation Finally, we **implement** the mapping aiming to make our test pass. We'll first set the target triple template,

```
:Planet/{id} :name "{name}"@en .
```

id and name have to come from the SQL source query,

```
select id, name from planets
```

id	name
Q308	Mercury
Q313	Venus
Q2	Earth
Q111	Mars
Q319	Jupiter
Q193	Saturn
Q324	Uranus
Q332	Neptune

The complete mapping declaration then becomes Listing 20. Inserting into the mapping declarations section of our *obda* file: **Note** that we do not need to repeat the pattern `:Planet/{id} a :Planet,`

```
mappingId planet_name
target    :Planet/{id} :name "{name}"@en .
source    select id, name from planets
```

Listing 20: Mapping declaration for planets' names.

as this statement is already mapped in the original mapping file.

After adding Listing 20, `solar_system.obda` reads (Listing 21) Does this make the test pass?

```
[PrefixDeclaration]
: http://example.org/planets#
dc: http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/
owl: http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#
rdf: http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
xml: http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace
xsd: http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#
obda: https://w3id.org/obda/vocabulary#
rdfs: http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
skos: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#
this: http://example.org/planets#
dcterms: http://purl.org/dc/terms/
planets: http://example.org/planets#

[MappingDeclaration] @collection [[
mappingId planet-id
target      :Planet/{id} a :Planet .
source      select id from planet

mappingId planet_name
target      :Planet/{id} :name "{name}"@en .
source      select id, name from planets

]]
```

Listing 21: *OBDA* mapping declarations file after adding the first two mappings.

2.7.10 Sum of planetary masses

Requirement Our next **requirement** is to be able to query the planetary masses. Masses are listed in the `mass` column in units of yottogram ($1\text{ yg} = 10^{27}\text{ kg}$). Pretty big numbers.

For example, Query 22 should return the sum of all planet's masses.

```
select (sum(?mass) as ?sum_of_masses)
where {
  ?planet a planets:Planet;
         planets:mass ?mass
}
```

Listing 22: **SPARQL** SELECT query asking for the sum over all planet's masses

Test Wrapped in a **ASK** query, we define the **test** (Query 23).

Run 23 this in your ontop query interface at <http://localhost:8080>. It will fail. To make it pass, we add the following mapping to our *obda* file:

Implementation

2.7.11 Max. orbital period

Requirement The longest planetary "year" is Neptune's with 5.2 billion seconds which amounts to 164 years on Earth. Let's assert we can run a query for the maximum orbital period:

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
ask where {
  {
    select (sum(?mass) as ?sum_of_masses)
    where {
      ?planet a planets:Planet;
              planets:mass ?mass
    }
  }
  filter(?sum_of_masses = 2667542)
}

```

Listing 23: SPARQL ASK query checking the correct sum of planetary masses

```

mappingId planet_mass
target    :Planet/{id} a :Planet ; :mass {mass}^^xsd:float .
source    select id, mass from planets

```

Listing 24: Mapping declaration for planetary masses

```

select (max(?orbital_period) as ?max_orbital_period)
where {
  ?planet a planets:Planet;
          planets:orbital_period ?orbital_period .
}

```

Test The corresponding ask query becomes

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
ask where {
  {
    select (max(?orbital_period) as ?max_orbital_period)
    where {
      ?planet a planets:Planet;
              planets:orbital_period ?orbital_period .
    }
  }
  filter(?max_orbital_period = 5200692224)
}

```

Listing 25: SPARQL ASK query checking the maximum orbital period.

Run it at <http://localhost:8080>.

Implementation The orbital period comes from the column `orbital_period` in our planet's DB, so the `sql` source becomes

```
select id, orbital_period from planets
```

and the complete mapping definition is

```

mappingId planet_orbital_period
target    :Planet/{id} a :Planet ; :orbital_period {orbital_period}^^xsd:float .
source    select id, orbital_period from planets

```

Insert the mapping into the *obda* file and re-run the test query Listing 25.

2.7.12 Min. distance to sun

Requirement Implement a mapping that allows to query for the planet's distance to the sun.

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
select (min(?distance) as ?min_distance)
where {
  ?planet a planets:Planet;
         planets:distance_to_sun ?distance .
}

```

Test Assert that planet Mercury has the shortest distance, about 70 million km.

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
ask where {
  {
    select (min(?distance) as ?min_distance)
    where {
      ?planet a planets:Planet;
             planets:distance_to_sun ?distance .
    }
  }
  filter(?min_distance = "69817442304"^^xsd:integer)
}

```

Listing 26: Test query for the shortest distance to the sun of all planets

Implementation We need the `distance_to_sun` column for each planet from the source query:

```
select id, distance_to_sun from planets
```

which, inserted into the mapping template, becomes

```

mappingId planet_distance_to_sun
target    :Planet/{id} a :Planet ;
          :distance_to_sun {distance_to_sun}^^xsd:float .
source    select id, distance_to_sun from planets

```

2.7.13 Rotational period

Requirement Besides the orbital period, we also want to be able to query the rotational period of our planets. An interesting number is the ratio of rotational period to orbital period or how long is a day compared to a year on each planet and which planet has the longest day compared to its year?

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
select ?name ?orbit_ratio
where {
  ?planet a planets:Planet ;
          planets:name ?name;
          planets:orbital_period ?orbit;
          planets:rotation_period ?rotation .
  bind((?rotation/?orbit) as ?orbit_ratio)
}
order by desc(?orbit_ratio)

```

Test Venus is the planet with the longest days in terms of its orbital period. Query 27 asserts this fact.

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
ask where {
  {
    select ?name ?orbit_ratio
    where {
      ?planet a planets:Planet ;
              planets:name ?name;
              planets:orbital_period ?orbit;
              planets:rotation_period ?rotation .
      bind((?rotation/?orbit) as ?orbit_ratio)
    }
    order by desc(?orbit_ratio)
    limit 1
  }
  filter(?name = "Venus"@en)
}

```

Listing 27: A SPARQL ASK query asserting that Venus has the longest rotational to orbital ratio.

Implementation To pass test query Listing 27, we need to map the rotational period in seconds coming from the `rotation_period` column in our planets DB:

```
select id, rotation_period from planets
```

id	rotation_period
Q308	5.0976e+06
Q313	2.0997e+07
Q2	86400
Q111	88642
Q319	35640
Q193	38520
Q324	61200
Q332	57600

The corresponding mapping becomes

```

mappingId planet_rotation_period
target    :Planet/{id} a :Planet; :rotation_period {rotation_period}^^xsd:float .
source    select id, rotation_period from planets

```

Insert this snippet in in the *obda* file and then run Query 27 in <http://localhost:8080>. It should return

```
true
```

2.7.14 Density and temperature

Requirement Density and temperature are among the most interesting but also among the most difficult to measure geophysical properties. Often, planetary scientists are interested in the so-called EOS¹³, that is the product of density and temperature. The corresponding query would be

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
select ?name ?eos
where {
  ?planet a planets:Planet ;
          planets:name ?name ;
          planets:temperature ?temperature;
          planets:density ?density .
  bind((?temperature*?density) as ?eos)
}
order by desc(?eos)
limit 1

```

Test As above, Venus has the highest EOS, we'll use this fact in a test query:

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
ask where {
  {
    select ?name ?eos
    where {
      ?planet a planets:Planet ;
              planets:name ?name ;
              planets:temperature ?temperature;
              planets:density ?density .
      bind((?temperature*?density) as ?eos)
    }
    order by desc(?eos)
    limit 1
  }
  filter(?name = "Venus"@en)
}

```

Listing 28: A SPARQL ASK query asserting Venus has the largest product of density and temperature.

¹³Equation of State

Implementation To enable and pass Query Listing 28, we have to map temperature and density values from the respective columns. The source query reads

```
select id, temperature, density from planets ;
```

id	temperature	density
Q308	700	5427
Q313	747	5243
Q2	288	5513
Q111	308	3933.5
Q319		1326
Q193	134	867
Q324	57	1271
Q332	72	1638

and the mapping then becomes

```
mappingId planets_eos
target    :Planet/{id} a :Planet;
          :temperature {temperature}^^xsd:float;
          :density {density}^^xsd:float .
source    select id, temperature, density from planets ;
```

Now run Query Listing 28 at <http://localhost:8080> and hopefully find false

2.7.15 Number of moons

We'll now map a **relation** between two **SQL** tables, **planets** and **moons**. The query we want to be able to run is asking for the number of moons per planet:

```
PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

SELECT DISTINCT ?planet_name (count(?moon) as ?moons)
WHERE {
  ?moon a planets:Moon ;
        planets:hasPlanet ?planet .
  ?planet a planets:Planet ;
          planets:name ?planet_name .
}
GROUP BY ?planet_name
ORDER BY ?moons
```

Listing 29: SPARQL SELECT query asking for the number of moons per planet

Note The numbers above are not accurate, they rather represent the current state of wikidata, which only contains 49 solar system moons.

To pass Query 29, we need to

Add class Moon to the ontology

```
## Moon
planets:Moon rdf:type owl:Class .
```

and classify every mapped record in the `moons` table as a class instance. As above, we could add target triples such as `:Moon/{id} a planets:Moon` to the mappings. Here, we follow a more elegant approach, making use of the ontology. The *planet-moon* relationship is established in the `mother_planet_id` of our `moons` table,

```
select id, mother_planet_id from moons order by id
```

id	mother_planet_id
Q15034	Q193
Q15037	Q193
Q15040	Q193
Q15047	Q193
Q15050	Q193
Q15629	Q324
Q15633	Q324
Q15637	Q324
...	...

Anything that has a mother planet must be a moon. Nowhere else in our database is a table with the `mother_planet_id` column. We'll express this defining feature of the `mother_planet_id` in our ontology. But let's first

declare a property `:hasPlanet` to express the *moon-planet* relationship.

```
## planets:hasPlanet
planets:hasPlanet a owl:ObjectProperty;
```

Only moons have a planet, we'll express this fact using the

```
rdfs:domain attribution,
rdfs:domain planets:Moon ;
```

In this way, every object having a `:hasPlanet` property, automatically becomes a `:Moon` class instance. Likewise, the object of a `hasPlanet` relation must be a `:Planet` instance. We express this fact by annotating `:hasPlanet` with `rdfs:range` as

```
rdfs:range planets:Planet ;
```

To go full circle, we also define the

inverse property

```
owl:inverseOf planets:hasMoon .
```

and define the latter as

```
## planets:hasMoon
planets:hasMoon a owl:ObjectProperty;
                rdfs:domain planets:Planet ;
                rdfs:range planets:Moon .
```

2.7.16 Mapping for *planet-moon* relation

Now we can develop our mapping as

```

mappingId planet_moon_relation
target    :Moon/{id} :hasPlanet :Planet/{mother_planet_id} .
source    select id, mother_planet_id from moons order by id

```

Can we now run Query 29?

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

SELECT DISTINCT ?planet_name (count(?moon) as ?moons)
WHERE {
  ?moon a planets:Moon ;
        planets:hasPlanet ?planet .
  ?planet a planets:Planet ;
         planets:name ?planet_name .
}
GROUP BY ?planet_name
ORDER BY ?moons

```

planet_name	moons
Neptune	1
Earth	2
Jupiter	8
Uranus	16
Saturn	22

Note that we do not explicitly state that records in the moons table are instances of class `planets:Moon`, yet Query 29, constraining `?moon a planets:Moon` works correctly.

2.7.17 Two moons for Earth

Wait, Earth has two moons? What are they? Can we run a query for the name of both moons?

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

select ?moon ?moon_name where {
  ?earth a planets:Planet;
        planets:name "Earth"@en .
  ?moon planets:hasPlanet ?earth ;
        planets:name ?moon_name .
}

```

Listing 30: SPARQL SELECT query asking for the name of Earth's moons

2.7.18 All moon properties

Requirement Implement mappings such that the following query works

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
select * where {
  ?planet a planets:Moon .
}

```

```

optional {?planet planets:apoapsis ?apoapsis .}
optional {?planet planets:density ?density .}
optional {?planet planets:radius ?radius .}
optional {?planet planets:orbital_period ?orbital_period .}
optional {?planet planets:mass ?mass .}
optional {?planet planets:temperature ?temperature .}
}

```

Test We wrap our **requirement** query in the **SPARQL ASK** query 31

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
ask where {
  {
    select * where {
      ?planet a planets:Moon .
      optional {?planet planets:apoapsis ?apoapsis .}
      optional {?planet planets:density ?density .}
      optional {?planet planets:radius ?radius .}
      optional {?planet planets:orbital_period ?orbital_period .}
      optional {?planet planets:mass ?mass .}
      optional {?planet planets:temperature ?temperature .}
    }
  }
}

```

Listing 31: SPARQL ASK query checking if a query returns all moon properties.

Implementation For the implementation, we first write the **SQL SELECT** source query asking for all literal properties of records in the moons table,

```
select id, name, apoapsis, density, radius, orbital_period, mass, temperature from moons
```

And insert that into the mapping Listing 32.

```

mappingId moon_physical_properties
target    :Moon/{id} a :Moon;
          :name "{name}"@en;
          :apoapsis {apoapsis}^^xsd:float;
          :density {density}^^xsd:float;
          :radius {radius}^^xsd:float;
          :orbital_period {orbital_period}^^xsd:float;
          :mass {mass}^^xsd:float;
          :temperature {temperature}^^xsd:float .
source    select id, name, apoapsis, density, radius, orbital_period, mass, temperature from moons

```

Listing 32: *OBDA* mapping for lunar properties

Confirmation Let's run Query 31 to confirm correctness of our mappings

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
ask where {

```

```

{
  select * where {
    ?planet a planets:Moon .
    optional {?planet planets:apoapsis ?apoapsis .}
    optional {?planet planets:density ?density .}
    optional {?planet planets:radius ?radius .}
    optional {?planet planets:orbital_period ?orbital_period .}
    optional {?planet planets:mass ?mass .}
    optional {?planet planets:temperature ?temperature .}
  }
}
true

```

2.7.19 Returning to two moons

Returning to the question about two terrestrial moons in our database, let's run Query 30, listed here again, for reference

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

```

```

select ?moon ?moon_name where {
  ?earth a planets:Planet;
    planets:name "Earth"@en .
  ?moon planets:hasPlanet ?earth ;
    planets:name ?moon_name .
}

```

moon	moon_name
http://example.org/planets#Moon/Q405	Moon
http://example.org/planets#Moon/Q3514088	Taiyin

So there are actually two moons in the database. What are their properties?

```

PREFIX : <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX planets: <http://example.org/planets#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

```

```

select ?moon ?prop ?val where {
  ?moon a planets:Moon;
    planets:hasPlanet ?earth;
    ?prop ?val .
  ?earth planets:name "Earth"@en .
}

```

```
order by ?moon ?prop
```

Hm, the mystery remains. Need to check Wikidata ...

2.8 Conclusions

This concludes the second part about mapping relational databases to **RDF**. What we covered:

- Configuration and startup of an ontop **SPARQL** endpoint
- Basics of the ontop mapping language OBDA

- Syntax of target triple templates
- Role of mapping ontologies
- Exercises on mapping literal and object relations
- Apply test driven development to SQL-to-RDF mapping

In the next section, we are going to apply our newly learned techniques to map bioimage metadata stored in an OMERO¹⁴ instance to RDF.

3 OMERO Virtualization

3.1 Learning Objectives

After finalizing this section, you will be able to

- investigate the schema of a **RDB**
- define **OBDA** mappings for many-to-many relations
- develop **OBDA** mappings in Protege¹⁵ with the ontop plugin¹⁶
- deploy an ontop **SPARQL** endpoint for your **OMERO** instance
- Run **SPARQL** queries to retrieve **OMERO** objects and metadata

3.2 OMERO

3.2.1 Background

In this section, we are finally going to work on a real biological database, **OMERO** (Allan et al. 2012). **OMERO** is for bioimage and life science image data what the photos app on your mobile phone is for your snapshots: A tool to store, organize, visualize, annotate, and share image data. **OMERO**, in combination with BioFormats (Moore et al. 2015), supports a plethora of image file formats including many proprietary formats such as dicom or czi. **OMERO** not only takes care of the image data itself (pixels) but also goes to great lengths to make image metadata findable, accessible and interoperable. Moreover, it provides means to extend image metadata by user generated tags, key-value pairs (map annotations), tables, files, comments, and ratings. More details on **OMERO** and the tools built around it are provided on the OME¹⁷ website <https://www.openmicroscopy.org>.

The aim of this section is to expose **OMERO** objects and their metadata as a (virtual) knowledge graph, accessible via **SPARQL** endpoint.

3.3 Preparations

3.3.1 Install Protege and the ontop plugin

See Appendices B.3 to B.4 for installation instructions on Protege and the ontop plugin.

3.3.2 Clone the omero-ontop-mappings repository

```
git clone https://github.com/German-Bioimaging/omero-ontop-mappings -b tutorial
```

Change into the cloned repository, `cd omero-ontop-mappings`. Then, deploy your endpoint. The following assumes **OMERO** is running in the `omero-test-infra` docker container on `localhost`.

¹⁴OME Remote Objects

¹⁵<https://protege.stanford.edu>

¹⁶<https://github.com/ontop/ontop/>

¹⁷Open Microscopy Environment

```

$ ./deployment_cookiecutter.sh
Ontop deployment configuration
Please enter database username (postgres user), password, and its URL, e.g.: localhost or host.example.com
Postgres user: postgres
DB password: postgres
DB host [localhost]: localhost

Enter PREFIX: RDF prefix for site instance, e.g. "iob".
prefix [ex]: swat
Enter URI: URI of site instance including trailing slash or #, e.g. "https://institute.of.bioimaging.com/".
site_uri [https://example.org/]: https://omeswat.org/

Setting public data mapping:
- YES  → Only data of the public user is mapped (enter that user\'s gls:omero ID).
- NO   → Enter SQL Condition on user_id that must evaluate to true to map object (e.g. "=2" or ">=0").
Only public data will be mapped to RDF? [yes]/no: no
Enter SQL condition on user_id (e.g. "=2", ">=0") [>=0]:

QLever SPARQL endpoint setup:
Do you want to create a QLever SPARQL endpoint serving the materialized RDF? [no]/yes: no

Preparing OBDA template for Cookiecutter ...

Running Cookiecutter ...
Set 600 on omero-ontop-mappings.properties
Creating deployment folder 'swat'...
'omero-ontop-mappings/omero-ontop-mappings.ttl' -> 'swat/swat.ttl'
'omero-ontop-mappings/catalog-v001.xml' -> 'swat/./catalog-v001.xml'
'omero-ontop-mappings/portal.toml' -> 'swat/./portal.toml'
'tmp/omero-ontop-config/omero-ontop-mappings.obda' -> 'swat/swat.obda'

Deployment folder created: swat/

Postgres user : postgres
db_host      : localhost
jdbc.url     : jdbc:postgresql://localhost:5432/omero
prefix       : swat
site_uri     : https://omeswat.org/
publiccond   : >=0

To start ontop endpoint:
cd swat
./swat-ontop-endpoint.sh

Materialization script created:
swat/swat-ontop-materialize.sh

```

3.3.3 Deployment

The deployed ontop config and mappings are then located in the `swat/` subdirectory and contain the following files

Filename	Description
<code>swat.obda</code>	ontop mappings file
<code>swat-ontop-endpoint.sh</code>	script to launch ontop endpoint
<code>swat-ontop-materialize.sh</code>	script to materialize to RDF
<code>swat.properties</code>	omero database connection details
<code>swat.ttl</code>	ontop ontology file
<code>portal.toml</code>	example queries
<code>catalog-v001.xml</code>	Ontology catalogue

3.3.4 Install ontop-cli

See Appendix B.2 to install ontop-cli.

3.4 Protege launch and config

We will now embark on a mapping development session in Protege.

- Launch Protege
- If not present, add ontotop tabs (Menu -> "Window" -> "Tabs" -> "Ontop Mappings")
- Configure postgres jdbc driver (see Figure 1)
 - Select "Menu" -> "File" -> "Preferences" -> "JDBC Drivers"
 - Click "Add"
 - Select "org.postgresql.Driver" from "Class name" dropdown menu
 - Select postgres jdbc driver jar file downloaded earlier in the ontotop-cli jdbc directory

Figure 1: Protege jdbc driver setup

- Setup connection (see Figure 2)
 - In the "Ontop Mappings" tab, select the "Connection parameters" subtab
 - Confirm and adjust the connection details

```

jdbc.user=postgres
jdbc.password=postgres
jdbc.url=jdbc:postgresql://localhost:15432/postgres
jdbc.driver=org.postgresql.Driver

```

Note: in contrast to the ontotop properties file, colons (:) must not be "\" escaped in the ontotop configuration dialogue.

Figure 2: Protege ontotop database connection configuration

3.5 Checking the first mapping

Select "Mapping manager" tab and double-click the first and only mapping, see Figure 3. You will find that the term `core:Image` is colored in red indicating problems with the mapping definition. Here, we are notified about an undefined term (`core:Image`).

Figure 3: Screenshot of the ontop mapping editor indicating missing ontology terms

3.6 Ontology imports

To remedy, we will import the OME Core ontology¹⁸ into our mapping ontology, see Figure 4.

- Close the mapping editor
- Open "Active ontology" tab
- Click "Direct Imports (+)" in the bottom panel
- Select "Import an ontology ... on the web"
- Enter

["https://german-bioimaging.github.io/ome-ld/_downloads/17de156c24f8ac1033e1c1979ab43646/model.owl.ttl"](https://german-bioimaging.github.io/ome-ld/_downloads/17de156c24f8ac1033e1c1979ab43646/model.owl.ttl)

into the URL field, see Figure 5.

- Click "Continue"
- After validating the ontology URL, you can finalize the import by clicking "Finish"
- Likewise import the Dublin Core `dcterms` ontology from https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/dublin_core_terms.ttl

Now select the "Entries/Classes" tab in Protege, which is now populated with all classes from the ome core and dublin core terms ontology (

¹⁸<http://german-bioimaging.github.io/ome-ld/>

Figure 4: Screenshot showing how to launch the ontology import dialogue

Figure 5: Screenshot of the ontology import dialogue in Protege

Figure 6: OME Core terms appear after importing the ontology

3.7 Optional: Site prefix

You may want to add a prefix to the ontology that sets the base part of your omero object URIs. E.g. for the IDR¹⁹, a sensible prefix could be "<http://idr.openmicroscopy.org/api/v0/m/>" In this way, the generated URIs for images, datasets, projects, etc. would resolve to the json api resources representing the respective object.

In the "Active ontology" tab, select "Ontology Prefixes" in the lower left, click (+) and enter the prefix name and URL (adjust according to your site).

Figure 7: Prefix editing dialogue in Protege

3.8 Recheck mapping

Now head back to the mapping editor and open the first mapping entry. The term `core:Image` is now highlighted in yellow, Protege's color for classes (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Protege onto mapping editor after fixing the missing ontology terms (compare to Figure 3).

3.9 Ontop queries

3.9.1 Starting the reasoner

Before running queries, we must start a reasoner. From "Menu" -> "Reasoner", select "Ontop 5.4.0" (or whatever version you have) and then again from the same menu, select "Start reasoner". The reasoner status shows up in the bottom right corner of the Protege window. If it says "Reasoner active", we can run our queries.

3.9.2 Running the query

From "Prefixes" in the top right corner, select all prefixes.

In the query editor window, enter a **SPARQL** query such as

¹⁹Image Data Resource

```
select * where {?s ?o ?p .}
```

and click "Execute". Results are displayed below the editor window (Figure 9). The "SQL translation" tab shows the rewritten **SQL** query.

Figure 9: Protege ontop **SPARQL** query editor and query response

3.10 Datasets

3.10.1 Requirement

Let's try to enable a query for **OMERO** datasets

```
SELECT * WHERE {
  ?dataset a core:Dataset;
}
```

Enter this query in the Ontop SPARQL query editor. It should return zero hits.

3.10.2 Implementation

Add the dataset mapping in the Ontop Mapping manager tab:

Target triples template

```
swat:Dataset/{id} a core:Dataset .
```

Source SQL query

```
select id from dataset
```

then save the new mapping by clicking "Create".

Figure 10: Mapping for OMERO datasets in the Protege-Ontop mapping editor

3.10.3 Confirmation

First restart the reasoner to pick up the last mappings ("Menu" -> "Reasoner" -> "Stop reasoner", "Start reasoner"). Then return to the SPARQL editor and re-run the query. It should now return three records (Figure 11).

Figure 11: SPARQL query for datasets (right) enabled by the second mapping (left).

3.11 Excursus: Many-to-many relations

The **OMERO** database is slightly more complex than the solar system example above. In particular, it contains not only one-to-many relations (as e.g. between planets and moons) but also many-to-many relations. An example is the relation between **OMERO Projects** and **OMERO Datasets**: A Project contains one or many Datasets and a Dataset is part of one or many Project. Many-to-many relations between two classes (tables) are typically represented by Link tables. A record (row) in the Link table (`projectdatasetlink`) represents one such a relation:

```
select id, child, parent from projectdatasetlink limit 10;
```

id	child	parent
1	1	1
2	2	1
3	3	1
4	4	2
5	5	2
6	6	2

Here, the `parent` column lists project ids, `dataset` ids are listed in the `child` column. E.g. `Project/1` contains `Dataset/1`, `Dataset/2`, and `Dataset/3`.

Conversely, to express many-to-many relation in **RDF**, we add as many triples to the graph as there are relations.

```
...
:Project/1 dcterms:hasPart :Dataset/1 ,
                    :Dataset/2 ,
                    :Dataset/3 .

:Project/2 dcterms:hasPart :Dataset/4 ,
                    :Dataset/5 ,
                    :Dataset/6 .
...
```

Note: We employ `dcterms:hasPart` and `dcterms:isPartOf` here to express the relationships between **Projects** and **Datasets**, adopting the corresponding semantics from the `ome-ld.owl` ontology Moore 2024. Surprisingly, `dcterms:isPartOf` and `dcterms:hasPart` are **not** defined as inverse properties of each other.

There are essentially two ways to go about many-to-many relationships in the case of **OMERO**:

1. Define mappings based on the Link tables alone

```
mappingId project-dataset-links
target: :Project/{parent} dcterms:hasPart :Dataset/{child} .
       :Dataset/{child} dcterms:isPartOf :Project/{parent} .
source: select parent, child from projectdatasetlink
```

1. Perform a LEFT JOIN operation between the native objects table (e.g. Project) and the Link table (e.g. ProjectDatasetLink)

```
mappingId project-datasets-joins
target :Project/{project_id} a core:Project ;
       rdfs:label {project_name} ;
       dcterms:hasPart :Dataset/{dataset_id} .
source select _project.id as project_id, _project.name as project_name, _projectdatasetlink.child
from project as _project left join projectdatasetlink as _projectdatasetlink on _project.id=_pro
```

3.11.1 Discussion

- Discuss pros and cons of these two approaches!
- Why did we use a LEFT JOIN (and not just a JOIN)?

3.11.2 Notes:

Using a LEFT JOIN in an atop mapping source query requires aliasing the two tables. Omitting this will lead to errors at startup or runtime. A JOIN operation is more relaxed about this.

3.12 Image-dataset relation

Now we can already query for images and datasets. How about finding out how many images reside in a dataset?

3.12.1 Requirements

We need to express that images belong to a certain dataset. We'll use the `dcterms:isPartOf` and `dcterms:hasPart` properties. Both should be part of the our Protege project (Figure 12).

Figure 12: `dcterms:hasPart` and `dcterms:isPartOf` properties in the "Annotation properties" tab

3.12.2 Test

We test by running Query 33.

```
select ?dataset (count(?image) as ?images)
where {
  ?dataset a core:Dataset;
          dcterms:hasPart ?image .
}
group by ?dataset
order by desc(?images)
```

Listing 33: SPARQL query counting image per dataset.

3.12.3 Implementation

A dataset can contain multiple images and an image may be part of multiple datasets, hence the image–dataset relation is a many–to–many relation. The OMERO database model encodes these relations in the `datasetimagelink` link table, queried by Listing 34.

```
select * from datasetimagelink
```

Listing 34: SQL query on `datasetimagelink`. The `parent` column lists datasets, `child` has the images.

id	permissions	version	child	creation_id	external_id	group_id	owner_id	update_id	parent
1	-120	0	1	356		0	0	356	1
2	-120	0	2	385		0	0	385	1
3	-120	0	3	414		0	0	414	2
4	-120	0	4	443		0	0	443	2
5	-120	0	5	472		0	0	472	2
6	-120	0	6	501		0	0	501	2
7	-120	0	7	530		0	0	530	2
8	-120	0	8	559		0	0	559	3
9	-120	0	9	588		0	0	588	3
10	-120	0	10	617		0	0	617	3
11	-120	0	11	646		0	0	646	2
12	-120	0	12	675		0	0	675	2

The query response table contains two foreign keys, `child` and `parent`, representing images and datasets, respectively. Each row defines a image–dataset relation. To express the image–dataset relation in our mappings, we add the target triple template Listing 35,

```
swat:Dataset/{dataset_id} dcterms:hasPart swat:Image/{image_id} .
```

Listing 35: OBDA triple template for image–dataset relations.

and the source query Listing 36,

to a new mapping in the Ontop Mapping editor.

3.12.4 Confirmation

After restarting the reasoner, the query should now return the number of images per dataset (Figure 13),

3.13 Annotations

Annotations are in the `annotation` table and mapped to RDF by (Listing 37).

3.13.1 Image Annotation links

Images and Annotations are another case of many–to–many relations. The link table is the `imageannotationlink` table. We express the image–annotation relations by the mapping 38.

```
select parent as dataset_id, child as image_id from datasetimagelink
```

Listing 36: SQL source query for image–dataset relations

Figure 13: Mapping (left) enabling SPARQL query (right) for dataset–image relations.

3.13.2 TODO Tags

Tags are annotations where the column discriminator has the value `/basic/text/tag/`. To select only tag annotations from the `annotation` table, we add a filter to our SQL query (Cref:

This will enable queries for image tags by

```
select ?image ?tag where {
  ?image a core:Image;
  core:hasAnnotation/core:tag ?tag .
}
```

4 Acknowledgements

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```
mappingId      annotation
target        swat:Annotation/{id} a core:Annotation .
source        select id from annotation.
```

Listing 37: OBDA mapping for Annotations.

```

mappingId image-annotations
target     swat:Image/{image_id} core:hasAnnotation swat:Annotation/{annotation_id} .
source     select parent as image_id, child as annotation_id from imageannotationlink

```

Listing 38: OBDA mapping for image-annotation relations

```

select id, discriminator, textvalue from annotation where annotation.discriminator='/basic/text/

```

Listing 39: SQL

```

mappingId tagannotation-id
target     swat:Annotation/{annotation_id} a core:TagAnnotation ;
                                                dc:identifier {annotation_id} ;
                                                core:tag "{textvalue}"^^xsd:string .
source     select id, textvalue from annotation where annotation.discriminator='/basic/text/tag/

```

Listing 40: OBDA mapping for tag annotations identified by the discriminator value.

image	tag
https://omeswat.org/Image/2	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/8	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/6	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/11	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/5	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/1	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/10	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/4	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/7	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/12	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/9	Screenshot
https://omeswat.org/Image/3	Screenshot

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Glossary

EOS Equation of State [26](#)

IDR Image Data Resource [37](#)

IRI Internationalized Resource Identifier [6](#), [14](#)

JDBC Java Database Connector [15](#)

KG Knowledge Graph [18](#)

OBDA Ontology Based Data Access [11](#), [13](#), [18](#), [32](#), [42–44](#)

OME Open Microscopy Environment [32](#)

OMERO OME Remote Objects [32](#), [38–40](#), [42](#), [47](#), [48](#)

R2RML Relational To RDF Mapping [13](#)

RDB Relational Database [11](#), [13](#), [15](#), [32](#)

RDF Resource Description Framework [4–6](#), [8](#), [10](#), [11](#), [13](#), [15](#), [31](#), [40](#), [42](#)

SPARQL SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language [11](#), [17](#), [18](#), [20–23](#), [25](#), [30–32](#), [37](#), [38](#), [42](#)

SQL Structured Query Language [5](#), [11](#), [13–15](#), [21](#), [27](#), [30](#), [38](#), [42–44](#)

W3C The World Wide Web Consortium [6](#)

5 Appendix

A Clone the tutorial repository

All content of this repository is maintained in one single git repository at <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/mpievolbio-scicomp/swat4hcls2026-ontop-tutorial>. Either clone

```
git clone https://gitlab.gwdg.de/mpievolbio-scicomp/swat4hcls2026-ontop-tutorial -b tutorial -d
```

or download the tutorial release from

B Software installations

B.1 apache-jena

B.1.1 Linux/UNIX/MacOS

In a user-writable directory (e.g. `$HOME/Downloads`), run

```
wget https://dlcdn.apache.org/jena/binaries/apache-jena-6.0.0.zip
unzip apache-jena-6.0.0.zip
rm apache-jena-6.0.0.zip
```

to download and unpack.

Then, install binaries and runtime libraries with

```
sudo install -v apache-jena-6.0.0/bin/* /usr/local/bin
```

and

```
sudo install -v apache-jena-6.0.0/lib/* /usr/local/lib
```

Choose a user-writable install target directory (e.g. under `$HOME/.local/` if `sudo` is not an option).

B.1.2 Windows

Either follow above instructions for Linux/UNIX/MacOS if you are running under Windows-Subsystem-Linux (WSL) **or**, copy point to the executables in the `bat/` directory of the downloaded and unpacked zip file downloaded from <https://dlcdn.apache.org/jena/binaries/apache-jena-6.0.0.zip>.

B.2 ontop-cli

In the tutorial directory, run Test your installation by running

```
source sh/install_ontop.sh
```

Listing 41: Download and install ontop-cli.

```
ontop help
```

which should produce

```
usage: ontop <command> [ <args> ]
```

Commands are:

<code>--version</code>	Show version of ontop
<code>bootstrap</code>	Bootstrap ontology and mapping from the database
<code>endpoint</code>	Start a SPARQL endpoint powered by Ontop
<code>extract-db-metadata</code>	Extract the DB metadata and serialize it into an output JSON file
<code>help</code>	Display help information
<code>materialize</code>	Materialize the RDF graph exposed by the mapping and the OWL ontology
<code>query</code>	Query the RDF graph exposed by the mapping and the OWL ontology
<code>validate</code>	Validate Ontology and Mappings
<code>mapping</code>	Manipulate mapping files

See `'ontop help <command>'` for more information on a specific command.

B.3 Protege

Protege is an open source, freely available desktop application for OWL and RDF editing. Download and install according to instructions at <https://protege.stanford.edu>.

B.4 Ontop plugin for Protege

The ontop plugin for Protege greatly enables mapping development in Protege. Get the ontop plugin from <https://github.com/ontop/ontop/releases>. Pick the `it.unibz.inf.ontop.protege-x.y.z.jar` file. This tutorial was developed with version 5.4.0 but you are free to pick the latest or any other version.

C Useful SQL queries

The following queries are useful to gather information about tables in the database while writing mappings

C.1 Tables in a database

```
select table_name from information_schema.tables where table_catalog='postgres' limit 10;
```

```
| table_name          |
|-----|
| pg_statistic        |
| pg_type             |
| pg_foreign_table    |
| pg_authid           |
| pg_shadow           |
| pg_roles            |
| pg_statistic_ext_data |
| pg_settings         |
| pg_file_settings    |
| pg_hba_file_rules   |
```

Note In `omero-test-infra`, all **OMERO** tables reside within the `postgres` database, while in production **OMERO** instances, they are in a dedicated database, often named `omero` or `omerodb` or similar.

C.2 List columns in a table

```
select column_name from information_schema.columns where table_name = 'image';
```

```
| column_name          |
|-----|
| id                  |
| acquisitiondate     |
| archived            |
| description         |
| permissions        |
| name                |
| partial             |
| series              |
| version             |
| creation_id         |
| external_id         |
| group_id            |
| owner_id            |
| update_id           |
| experiment          |
| fileset             |
| format              |
| imagingenvironment |
```

```
| instrument      |  
| objectivesettings |  
| stagelabel     |
```

D OMERO Data model

The complete **OMERO** data model is documented at <https://ome-model.readthedocs.io/en/stable/developers/model-overview.html>